

Additional instructions for planning the management of confidential and personal data

Introduction

These instructions offer additional guidance for planning the handling of confidential and personal data, and are to be used alongside the [general Finnish DMP guidance](#). Confidential and personal data may often be referred to as sensitive data.

Note that research organisations provide guidance for researchers on complying with the principles of data protection and information security. Please familiarise yourself with your organisation's data management guidelines and, if needed, contact your home organisation's support services.

We have arranged the instructions under each numbered section of the data management plan (DMP) so that you will first find the guidelines on what to write in each section, then practical **Tips for best practices** to ease the writing process, and finally some useful **Links** concerning that specific section.

The data can include both confidential data and personal data. These data types are described below.

Types of *confidential data*:

- Data that are confidential or secret based on legislation (such as national defense)
- Data that are trade secrets (e.g., innovations that may lead to patents)
- Data that are under a non-disclosure agreement
- [Sensitive species data](#), such as data concerning endangered animals and plants, data related to nature conservation or biosafety
- Data that are confidential by agreement between partners (such as unpublished research data, data from business partners)
- Unpublished research data

Types of *personal data* (all data from which a person can be identified either *directly* or *indirectly*):

- *Direct identifiers*: These can include a name, phone number, personal identity code, image, audio, fingerprint, dental chart or MRI image.
- *Indirect identifiers*: Examples of these are gender, age, education, professional status, nationality, location data, career history, system log data, marital status, place of residence or vehicle registration number.
- [Special categories of personal data](#) are any data whose disclosure could harm the study subjects. They are related to health, sexual orientation, ethnic background, trade union membership or religious conviction. In [the General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#) their processing is heavily regulated.
- In addition, there can be other types of personal data that are sensitive by nature. **The parties carrying out the research are responsible for identifying these data**, such as information about the use of social welfare services and status as a debtor, among other things.

Note that when handling any kind of personal data, you must acknowledge and address [the seven principles of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation](#) in the different sections of your DMP.

Note that there are different levels of confidentiality. For example, there are different categories of personal information (personal data and special categories of personal data), which require different kinds of management. The same applies to all confidential data. Please check your organisation's guidance on information classification and information security.

Links

- [Data protection principles](#) (Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman)
- [What is personal data?](#) (Finnish Social Science Data Archive)
- [Processing of personal data](#) (Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman)

1. General description of data

1.1 What kinds of data is your research based on? What data will be collected, produced or reused? What file formats will the data be in? Additionally, give a rough estimate of the size of the data produced/collected.

If your data includes confidential or personal data, you need to describe them in this section of the DMP. These data will need special attention in data handling, which you will describe in other sections.

Note that the researcher is responsible for recognising whether their data will include confidential data, personal data or special categories of personal data. Interview recordings, for instance, always contain direct identifiers (e.g., vocal recordings or facial images of the study subject). In addition, surveys that contain open-ended questions most likely include at least indirect identifiers. Medical imaging data are often considered personal data. Even technical measurement data from a certain device are personal data if a measurement can be associated with an individual person (e.g., GPS tracker information).

Further, if the researcher will process personal data in the project, it is important to plan the pseudonymisation and/or the anonymisation of the data beforehand.

Pseudonymous and anonymous data:

- *Pseudonymisation* refers to removing or replacing identifiers with pseudonyms or codes, which are kept separately and protected.
 - Pseudonymous data becomes *anonymous* when separately kept identifying information (decryption key, personal data and information on the techniques used to pseudonymise the data) are destroyed and even by combining indirect identifiers, the data can no longer be linked to the original personal data.
- The *data are anonymous* if they cannot be linked to the original personal data through reasonable effort.
- Anonymous data are no longer categorised as personal data, which affects the processing of the data after the anonymisation.

Tips for best practices

- A table is a good way to address all the questions in this section. List all your datatypes in a table and add an extra column assigning whether the datatype includes confidential or personal data. You can then refer to the table and datasets described in it later in the DMP. In this table you can also specify the owners, [controllers and processors of the data](#); see section 2.1.

Links

- [Anonymisation and identifiers](#) (Finnish Social Science Data Archive)
- [Pseudonymised and anonymised data](#) (Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman)

1.2 How will the consistency and quality of data be controlled?

Explain how the data collection, analysis and processing methods used may affect the quality of the data and how you will minimise the risks related to data accuracy.

Data quality control ensures that no data are accidentally changed and that the accuracy of the data is maintained over its entire lifecycle. Quality problems can emerge due to the technical handling, converting or transferring of data, or during its contextual processing and analysis. Furthermore, processes such as pseudonymisation and anonymisation can affect data quality (see section 1.1).

Tips for best practices

- Remember the difference between pseudonymised and anonymised data.
- Remember also to discuss how minimisation, pseudonymisation, and anonymisation affect data quality.

Links

- [Anonymisation and identifiers](#) (Finnish Social Science Data Archive)
- [Pseudonymised and anonymised data](#) (Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman)

2. Ethical and legal compliance

2.1 What legal issues are related to your data management (for example, GDPR and other legislation affecting data processing)?

Legal issues

In this section, please specify any legislation that is relevant to your research project. These might include legislation that governs the processing of personal data such as the GDPR, the Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data, the Finnish Biobank Law, or other legislation such as EU medical device regulation.

Confidential data

When working with external parties, for instance, in a consortium or with businesses, make sure that agreements on data handling and management are drawn up. Plan the safe handling of confidential data according to these agreements and any non-disclosure agreements. Consider export restrictions and seek advice from your organisation if you think these apply

to your research. Show in the DMP that you are aware of the relevant legislation that governs the publicity and handling of the data you have.

If your research includes work that may be patented, get in touch with your organisation's data support or innovation services about how to protect the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

Personal data and [special categories of personal data](#)

If you plan to process personal data, you must plan the lifecycle of personal data processing before the data processing starts. Note that specific GDPR requirements must be followed when processing [special categories of personal data](#).

The [processing of personal data](#) means any operation which is performed on personal data, such as collection; recording; organisation; use; storage; adaptation or alteration; disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making the data available; alignment or combination or restriction or erasure or destruction. Processing personal data in Finland is regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the [Finnish Data Protection Act](#) and specific legislation (such as the Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data or the Act on the Protection of Privacy in Working Life).

Any research that gathers information from or about individuals will need a *privacy notice*. The privacy notice is provided to the research participants. Keep the privacy notice updated and inform the research participants of any changes. Check your own organisation's templates for a suitable privacy notice.

The GDPR defines the information content required for the privacy notice. Among the required information are the purpose of processing personal data and its [legal basis](#). The legal basis with research is typically "[scientific research, a task in the public interest](#)" or "[consent](#)". Organisations have their own guidelines on which legal basis you should use. If the legal basis is "consent", all usage purposes of the data must be distinctly specified both in the [privacy notice](#) and in the [form for obtaining a participant's consent to process personal data](#). If these uses of data change, the participants must be informed, and consent must be obtained again. Consent to process personal data is different from ethical consent to participate. See below for more information on ethical consent to participate.

When processing personal data, plan and mention in this section of the DMP who or what organisation is the [data controller](#) of the data you collect or produce. If two or more parties act as [joint controllers](#), the data processing must be agreed upon in advance according to your organisation's guidelines (e.g., with a joint controllership agreement).

Mention if there are [processors](#) who process the personal data on behalf of the controller. The data controller is required to inform the research participants when personal data are processed by a processor. Include this information in the privacy notice. A *Data Processing Agreement* (DPA) is required for external processors of data with whom your organisation does not yet have a DPA. These third parties could include collaborators, transcription companies, translation services or IT solution providers. The DPA provides instructions for data processing. In the DMP you should identify a possible need for a DPA and state that you will make the necessary agreements.

When the processing of personal data is likely to result in a high risk to an individual's rights and freedoms, a *data protection impact assessment* (DPIA) is a legal requirement. Find out

your organisation's guidance and process for this, and mention this in the DMP if it is relevant for your research.

If you think you may need to transfer personal data outside of the EU/EEA, outline the planned process and get in touch with your organisation's legal team or data protection officer regarding the required documentation, such as a *data transfer agreement*.

Note that all data protection documentation must be prepared before the personal data processing starts.

For the purposes of the DMP, list which data protection documents you will need to prepare. These might include

- A privacy notice
- An assessment of data protection risks or data protection impact assessment (DPIA)
- Ethical consent to participate
- Consent to process personal data
- A data processing agreement (DPA)

In order to comply with the data protection regulation and fulfil the principle of accountability, compile and preserve your data protection documentation according to the instructions of your own organisation. Remember that a DMP can be a part of the data protection documentation. Make sure that all the documents are aligned, especially the research plan, DMP and any other possible personal data documentation or legal agreements.

Ethical reviews and considerations

Find out from your organisation if your research requires an *ethical review*. Mention the need for an ethical review in the DMP. An ethical review is mandatory in medical research (Medical Research Act 986/1999). In human sciences, an ethical review is required if the study meets one of the six specific criteria defined by the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK) in the publication [‘The ethical principles of research with human participants and ethical review in the human sciences in Finland’](#). Take into account that some publishers and funders may require an ethical review. **An ethical review can only be carried out prior to data collection.**

When individuals are involved in research, *ethical consent to participate* needs to be obtained from the participants. Informed consent to participate in a study is a fundamental premise for all research involving human subjects, both in medicine and in the human sciences.

Assess if there are other ethical considerations regarding your data, such as sensitive species data, sensitive location data or the use of artificial intelligence. If these apply, seek advice from your organisation.

Tips for best practices

- A good place to start is your own organisation's instructions. Refer to their templates (for documents such as the privacy notice, consent form, risk assessment, data protection impact assessment).
- Contact your own organisation's data protection officer, data support personnel or legal services if needed.

Links

- [Data Protection Ombudsman](#)
- [Finnish National Board on Research Integrity: Advice and materials](#)
- [Scientific research and data protection](#) (Data Protection Ombudsman)

2.2 How will you manage the rights of the data you use, produce and share?

Specify in the DMP who will own the data, have access to the data and what agreements will be made to define data responsibilities and ownership.

Agreements on *data ownership* and other *intellectual property rights* must be concluded before commencing any actual research activities. These define the processing of the data in many ways.

The data processing agreement (DPA) defines the conditions for personal data processing performed by a processor (see section 2.1).

When working with confidential data, consider whether *non-disclosure agreements* are needed for researchers or third parties.

When using pre-existing data, consider what *permissions and data access agreements* are needed to access and use these data. Ensure you handle the data and delete it as specified by the data controller or owner. If you wish to archive the anonymised data at the end of the research, be sure to include any plans for archiving the anonymised data in your data request or research permit.

Please also find out whether the funder of your research, owner of the data or any other external party has any claims concerning the data.

Template agreements are provided by your own research organisation, as well as consultation on making agreements, obtaining permissions and addressing the IPR aspects of the data that you plan to collect or reuse.

3. Documentation and metadata

3.1 How will you document your data in order to make it findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable for you and others? What kind of metadata standards, README files or other documentation will you use to help others to understand and use your data?

When describing data, please remember that file and folder names as well as variables, codings and metadata may contain confidential or personal data. Even if your research data contains personal data, related metadata can be published if it does not contain identifiers which could be used to identify a study subject.

Tips for best practices

- *If my research data includes confidential and/or personal data, what documentation can be included in the metadata?*
 - Although the actual values of the variables used in the data are confidential, you can make **your codebook** (the variable names and the descriptions of the variables) **openly available**.

- Interview or survey questions can also be opened alongside the metadata without compromising data protection regulation, **unless restricted by copyright**.
- It is good practice to include the privacy notice, a template for a consent form, and electronic lab notes into the metadata.
- At a minimum, you can open a general description of your research topic and data, and **distribute** your contact information so that other researchers can find your valuable research.

Links

- [Making a research project understandable – Guide for data documentation](#) (in Zenodo by Helsinki University Library)
- [Data description and metadata](#) (Finnish Social Science Data Archive)

4. Storage and backup during the research project

4.1 Where will your data be stored, and how will the data be backed up?

A risk assessment is used to determine the required protective measures for the entire lifecycle of the data, particularly storage solutions and data processing platforms (see also section 4.2).

According to the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#), risks related to the processing of personal data must be assessed before processing any such data. Familiarise yourself with the national and organisational data protection and risk management guidelines and consider the following:

- Which freedoms and [rights](#) of the data subject can be compromised by the processing?
- What kind of damage can the planned processing of personal data cause to the data subject?
- What kind of damage can the inappropriate disclosure, destruction or corruption of the data cause to the data subject?
- What kind of risks must your data be protected against?
- What measures are used to manage the identified risks?
- What is an accepted level for the probability and impact of residual risks?

Note that health and social data from the public register (processing under secondary-use law) can be processed only in the audited environments listed in [Valvira's TOINI register](#). These data can be accessed only if researchers have a permit from the data controller and the data is available only in the registered research environment.

Please familiarise yourself with your organisation's information classification and the related instructions on sensitive data storage services, data sharing and the tools with which information security is ensured in the processing of data. Also find out the service address of your organisation's data protection and IT units.

[CSC Sensitive Data](#) services support national requirements for sensitive data and comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Using [SD Connect](#) you can store and share encrypted sensitive data, and using [SD Desktop](#) you can create a private workspace to compute sensitive data.

Tips for best practices

- Preferably use a storage and computing service designed for sensitive data management offered by your home organisation, offered nationally (e.g., CSC) or services based in the EU.
 - Do the storage services maintain a log on data use?
 - Can the data be accessed remotely, and how is remote access protected?
 - Also consider your organisation's instructions regarding AI tools for research, especially in terms of confidential and personal data.
- Describe which parts of the data are encrypted, which tools are to be used, and who is responsible for the encryption names and passwords.
- Check how and when backup copies are made in the storage services used and whether automatic backups are provided.
- Please note that even if you plan to pseudonymise or anonymise your data, you will have to plan the storage and computing services according to the current (or initial) level of sensitivity or confidentiality of the data.

Links

- [Risk assessment](#) (Data Protection Ombudsman)
- [Impact assessment](#) (Data Protection Ombudsman)

4.2 Who will be responsible for controlling access to your data, and how will secured access be controlled?

Access to confidential or personal data must be limited [throughout the data's entire lifecycle](#) to those individuals for whom it is necessary in order to carry out the research. Data can be accessible only with expressly granted permission. Please take into account that this group also includes the parties that maintain the services and equipment used and other external service providers, if any.

Please familiarise yourself with the principles, guidelines and tools related to the management of access rights in your organisation. Find out how misuse and damage related to personal data are reported in your organisation.

Tips for best practices

- How is user and access control implemented, and who is responsible? Access is only granted when needed, and the access must be as limited as possible. A system must be in place for revoking and deleting access rights regularly.
 - How do user right requirements vary by data?
- How is the use of data and its appropriateness monitored? This means both a technical log and procedures for monitoring the processing and use of the data.
- Minimise the data and avoid unnecessary copies. This means that you should only process/manage the data that is absolutely needed.
- How are the facilities used for the data protected?
- Who can transfer data from one party to another and on what grounds, and what are the protocols for secure data transfer? This must be in line with the consent from the data subjects if the data has been made available based on consent.

- A Data Transfer Agreement is necessary if personal and sensitive data are shared with collaborators affiliated with organisations in non-EU /EEA countries.

5. Opening, publishing and archiving the data after the research project

5.1 What part of the data can be made openly available or published? Where and when will the data, or its metadata, be made available?

Publishing datasets that contain confidential or personal data cannot be done in the same manner as non-confidential datasets. You need to carefully consider the option suitable for your dataset and use special caution. Please familiarise yourself with the principles and guidelines in your organisation and contact your organisation's data support services for help.

The following forms of publishing are recommended:

1. Publish the discovery metadata of your dataset in a research database or another publishing service, preferably in a structured form. Make the actual data available subject to permission from the producer of the data or a reliable data repository.
2. Anonymise the data and publish the anonymised data in a data repository. This is recommended as anonymised data no longer constitutes personal data and is no longer subject to data protection legislation, which makes accessing and opening it possible.
 - a. Data is considered anonymous if there is no means to link the data back to an individual (see section 1.1). In addition, the identification key must be destroyed. GDPR does not regulate data that are anonymous.
 - b. Pseudonymised data still constitutes personal data. Opening it for others can only be done by following GDPR principles and rules.
3. Use services designed for publishing confidential and personal data under controlled access such as [CSC SD Submit](#) (pilot phase) or [Federated EGA](#) (for genome-phenome data), and enable its reuse with [SD Apply](#) (pilot phase).

Datasets that contain personal data can be disclosed to interested parties who have been granted a permit for a purpose corresponding with the original grounds for processing. The original grounds for processing datasets containing personal data, such as statutory grounds or consent, can restrict any further use. For example, if the original consent form does not cover the further use of the data, opening the dataset may require requesting fresh consent from the data subjects.

Links

- [Anonymisation and personal data](#) (Finnish Social Science Data Archive)
- [Pseudonymised and anonymised data](#) (Office of Data Protection Ombudsman)
- [Metadata publishing service Etsin](#)

5.2 Where will data with long-term value be archived, and for how long?

This section of the DMP determines what happens to the research data after the research project. Usually the data handling that takes place after the research project is dictated by contractual and juridical frameworks (e.g., Archives Act 831/1994, Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data, data permit), and can include either disposing of the research data after the original research purpose has been concluded or archiving the research data.

For archiving to be a viable option, it must be carefully planned before collecting the data, informing the subjects and making agreements so that these processes enable archiving. If you are managing confidential or personal data with long-term value, please contact your home organisation support services to plan these properly. Archiving should always be done by depositing the data in a proper archive (e.g., an institutional archive), which will then take care of handling the data.

Archiving research datasets with personal data is possible on the grounds of complying with the [Data Protection Act](#). Based on the Data Protection Act (Article 4.4), the processing of personal data for archiving purposes is necessary and proportionate to the aim of public interest. Exceptions to the restrictions are made for the processing of special categories of personal data for archiving purposes in the public interest in accordance with the Data Protection Act (Article 6.8). Archived sets of (personal) data are no longer actively used for the original purpose. In these cases the archive decides on how long the data is archived, so it is not the responsibility of the researcher. To preserve archived data in the long term, organisational archives can use the [Digital Preservation Service for Research Data](#).

You should erase all personal data when it is no longer required by its original purposes of processing. Simply deleting a file and emptying the recycle bin is not enough. Deleted data can be recovered even after reformatting the hard disk. There is software available for the permanent disposal of data based on, for example, overwriting or demagnetising hard disks. Storage devices can also be mechanically crushed into an unreadable state. See the guidelines of your own organisation for how to safely dispose of your data.

Tips for best practices

- Information about data archiving should be provided in the privacy notice given to the study subjects.
- Please remember that the anonymisation and disposal or archiving of data must be carried out by the expiry date of the relevant research permit.
- Many institutions of higher education and research institutions have internal guidelines and recommendations for the disposal of data and storage equipment; consult your organisation's data support or IT about these before planning the disposal of data.
- Find out the requirements of the archive you are planning to use. These might include informing research participants of the archiving in the privacy notice.

Links

- [Disposal of research data](#)
- [Destruction, anonymisation or archiving of data at the conclusion of the research](#)
- [Storage limitation](#) (Office of Data Protection Ombudsman)

6. Data management responsibilities and resources

6.1 Who (for example role, position and institution) will be responsible for data management?

Though the PI carries the overall responsibility for the project, specify in the DMP what data management tasks and responsibilities the project members will take on.

For example, mention who is responsible for

- Ensuring that the research team is trained on processing confidential or personal data
- Carrying out the risk assessment and possible ethical reviews for the project
- Preparing the privacy notice, publishing it and keeping participants informed
- Managing confidential and personal data as well as monitoring its quality throughout the lifecycle of the data
- Preparing instructions on data processing for DPAs when working with external personal data processors
- Ensuring data protection and information security
- Overseeing the anonymisation/pseudonymisation process
- Preparing the data for archiving and opening
- Safely disposing of personal data once the project has finished

Consider whether these responsibilities will be shared with partners or external parties, for example, in cases of joint controllership.

6.2 What resources will be required for your data management procedures to ensure that the data can be opened and preserved according to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

This covers both direct costs to the project as well as personnel hours spent on data management.

The foundation for creating FAIR data is embedded into everyday working practices (file naming, documentation, agreements, etc.). The estimated time required for this depends on the data management responsibilities (see section 6.1) of the project members.

When planning the *resources* needed, the following must be taken into account:

- Costs of data minimisation, pseudonymisation and anonymisation, or the time spent and software required for the task
- Requirements set by a higher level of security for the activities and solutions used, as well as related additional costs
- Costs associated with services, permissions or access to data (e.g., FINDATA)
- Costs associated with archiving and opening data
- Costs associated with disposing of data
- Time spent preparing the dataset for opening and considering personal data/confidentiality issues
- Consultation with an expert to check the quality of the data (e.g., whether a dataset is anonymous)